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RIVER RAFTING AND CAMPING AS AN ADVENTURE FORM OF TOURISM FOR SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOOD ENHANCEMENT

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Abstract

Uttarakhand is known all over India and world as a place of breathtaking natural beauty and well known for tourism destination for different type of tourism. One of the important such adventure activities is Ganga basin white water river rafting and beach camping which is an amazing adventurous as well as major source of income for the local community & revenue generation for the state. Mostly Indian tourists are keenly participation for beach camping and rafting along with flying fox, kayaking and rock climbing. The ratio of visited tourist in rafting and camping site is about 70% of Indian Tourist and 30% of Foreigner tourist up to last year (2014-15). The result indicates that due to improper management and lack of development directional approach from state agencies and relevant department and contribution of these agencies remained quiet for socio-economic development. Eco-tourism shapes as industry and government observed as an appropriate sector to create jobs, international income and to stimulate regional development.

Key words: River Rafting, Adventure, Tourism, Sustainable, Livelihood

Introduction

A large number of tourism activities have been developed in the last decade not only in India even worldwide. Some of these tourism activities are Nature Based Tourism, Sustainable Tourism, Green Tourism, Village Tourism, Adventurous Tourism, Responsible Tourism, Adventurous Tourism and Eco-tourism are often used and in line with the general development. Today most people involved in the local tourism industry have realized that a change in strategy and attitude is long overdue (**Knuth, 2005**). The general notion of tourism is that it promotes economic activity, boosts the local production of resources and helps in infrastructure development without paying attention to the negative socio-cultural impacts (**Farooque, 2008**). There are many example for tourism destination where rapid and unplanned development has produced over-reliance on this one industry and environment degradation. Eco-tourism not only offers an alternative livelihood for the communities in the region but also preserves the environment and culture of the region through involvement of the civil society. Adventurous Tourism i.e. river rafting, kayaking, paragliding, rock climbing, skiing and more activities are the major part of ecotourism at local areas.

Literature Review:

[Ashok Kumar Sahani / River Rafting and Camping As an Adventure Form of Tourism for Sustainable Livelihood Enhancement](#)

Uttarakhand is known all over India and world as a place of breathtaking natural beauty and well known for tourism destination for different type of tourism. One of the important such adventure activities in Ganga basin is white water river rafting and beach camping which is an amazing adventurous as well as major source of income for the locality & revenue generation for forest and Tourism department. But mostly Indian tourists are keenly participation for beach camping and rafting along with flying fox, kayaking and rock climbing. The ratio of visited tourist in rafting and camping site is about 70% of Indian Tourist and 30% of Foreigner tourist up to last year (2013-14). The result indicates that due to improper management and lack of development directional approach from state agencies and relevant department and contribution of these agencies remained quiet for socio-economic development (**Sarathi, et al, 2011**). Tourism shapes as industry and government observed as an appropriate sector to create jobs, international income and to stimulate regional development (**Hall, 1991**).

Tehri Garhwal is one of the sacred hilly districts of Uttarakhand State where lots of valley and high mountainous for adventurous activities like river rafting, paragliding, kayaking, rock climbing, jumping fox, parasailing and more. River rafting on the Ganga River is one of the best adventurous sites where arrival of tourist is increasing day by day wherein the participation of foreigner tourist is increasing specially for river rafting. From Kaudiyala to Tapovan near Rishikesh is known as “Kaudiyala-Tapovan Ecotourism Zone” and also popular for safe river rafting site. The study site is situated along the Badrinath Highway (NH 58) on River Ganga in Tehri Garhwal District of Uttarakhand, between 30°04’23” and 30°07’34” N latitude and 78°30’13” and 78°19’48”E longitude and covering a road distance of 40 km (Kaudiyala to Rishikesh). Devprayag is a confluence point of the two rivers Bhagirathi and Alkananda and from there it is known as the holy Ganga. Tourism shapes as industry and government observed as an appropriate sector to create jobs, international income and to stimulate regional development (**Hall, 1991**). Singtali and Shivpuri are two sites with almost 50-60 percent of rafting and camping activities are done and providing 85-90 percent of employment to local people. There is also indicates negative impact of river rafting activities due to inability of the environment to cope with the visitor use and expanding of the national highway within the acceptable limits of change (**Farooque et al 2008**). Due to myriad visitors for river rafting activities can create lots of environmental disturbance and threaten. Pollution due to increased vehicular emission, traffic congestion and unplanned construction are adversely impacting the society and pose threat to change in local climate (**Mahapatra, 2011**).

The purpose of the study is to find out the socio-economic impact of local communities through river rafting on the Ganga River also identify the impact of Kedar Valley disaster on river rafting. The study high light and identify the impact of the rafting activities keeping in mind the past research status along with improvement of economic transition during the decade. The blue color water of the Ganga became silver color with the sun light which attracts lots of tourists every time for its scenic beauty. There are many wild animals i.e. leopard, wild fox, black monkey, langur, tiger, bear & many birds are living in the dense forest alongside of the Ganga which is an attraction for tourist during their camping on the river beach. There are around 15-20 villages between Kaudiyala-Tapovan Ecotourism Zone wherein Kaudiyala, Singtali, Atali, Byasi and Gular village’s about 50-60% people are mostly benefited and engaged in camping and river rafting either directly or indirectly. Table No-1& 2 depict the participation of villagers in the river rafting and related activities.

The Ganga valley is dense and fully covered forest area and both side of river Ganga has great potential for Eco-tourism and sustainable livelihood option for local communities. There are 85-90%

villagers involve in river rafting and beach camping along with rock climbing, trekking, village tour and more. As per the status of arrival tourist for adventurous activities it is increasing every year and tourists are participating in all adventurous activities as a result the involvement and interest of local peoples in river rafting and related activities are increasing which has directly or indirectly secured their livelihood. The economic condition and living standard of local people has improved from just few last 4-5 years because of this tourism activity. As per the data of 2006-07, there was some part-time employment of local people as cooks, river guide, drivers and daily-wage labors and the average income of these people was varied from Rs 1500 to 2500 per month plus free boarding & lodging but it is observed that in 2013-14, there are mostly full time employment of local people in different position according to their skill and education and the average income of these people is varied from 6000 to 10,000 per month plus free boarding and lodging which is increase of forth-fold to old salary to the past (Table No- 3). On other hand, based on the ground observation and analysis, some measure and improvement are recommended for environment protection and increase community interest in eco tourism within policy and guideline for rafting and beach camping.

At present there are about 132 companies working on river rafting and beach camping wherein 30-40% companies are providing both rafting and beach camping facility and 50-60% companies owner are local and operate and manage themselves. From 1998-99 to at present the number of companies has increased every year and numbers of tourist has also increased at the same rate (*Table- 4& 5: Permit of License for Rafting and Camping year wise*). As per the statistical data of arrival of tourists for rafting and camping, the graph of Indian tourists has decreased and seemed less interest for the same due to the impact of disaster while the graph of foreigner tourists has increase according to the last year. With the conclusion, we can say that disaster in Ganga valley has less impacted on tourists graph for the river rafting and other activities. (*Table- 6: Statistics of arrival of tourists before and after disaster in river rafting*).

Impact of Kedar Valley disaster on River Rafting

The impact of Kedar valley disaster in 2013 mostly affected to Char Dham Yatra and also affected of inflow of tourist across the India and over the world to the state. The data shows that arrival of tourist before disaster was 284.33 Lakh including 282.92 Lakh were Indian and 1.41 Lakh were Foreigner. But after the disaster the inflow of the tourist has decreased and it became 201.15 Lakh which include 225.47 Lakh Indian and 0.90 were foreigner tourists. Above statics of tourist shows that due to impact of disaster people are ignoring such a spiritual and mass tourism. The disaster in Kedar Valley, Kaudiyala-Tapovan rafting and camping zone has also affected especially at beach site where rafting companies were facilitate to beach camps. As per discussion with camps owner they said that every company was get away from the camp site after mid-June and all river activities stopped till mid-September but the tourists comes continuously till end of the June for rafting and kayaking due to hot month of the year. Local people are fully engaged that time for their different services. After the heavy disaster working process has little get down due to the facing of less arriving of tourists according to past year. Most of the local owners who have start-up their companies for rafting and camping have specially faced the challenges and boost up their socio-economic among the competing companies.

Ashok Kumar Sahani / River Rafting and Camping As an Adventure Form of Tourism for Sustainable Livelihood Enhancement

The heavy disaster in Kedar Valley came during third week of June'13. According to guideline of Forestry and Tourism Department, any company cannot stay at camp site after the mid-June. In this order most of the companies have get away from the beach site but some company's tent and other material was remaining at site and all the material ran off in heavy flood but there has no human casualties found during heavy disaster. But most of the beach site areas were affected where all sand has been run off in heavy flood whereby most of the companies have faced the shortage of sand for place tent and also their specific landmark for tent and other things for every company have also ran off during the heavy disaster.

Meanwhile, those people have shifting toward the river rafting activity instead of Char Dham Yatra mostly for enjoyment/recreational activities.. Due to nearby of Rishikesh and increasing myriad tourists for such activities can be create major threat on environment and ecological. As the interest of tourist will enhance for river rafting and camping activities it will lead to increase in demand of camp site and tents whereby it will impact to environmental and ecological balance at certain area and increase anthropogenic pressure during such activities. Aquatic habitat of various fauna and nearby flora will be affect on riverine during rafting activity. As per the statement of local people, the presence of wild animal i.e. Leopard (*Panthera pardus*), Sambar (*Cervus unicolor*), Barking Deer (*Muntiacus muntjak*) and more in surrounded forest of Ganga Valley is decreasing every year due to heavy vehicle sound in NH 58, myriad anthropogenic pressure during river rafting activities and due to that their natural habitat is being affected and some wild animal species are gradually migrate to other areas whereby it can also affects animal food cycle as well as ecosystem pyramid at certain place. Apart from that, Langur (*Presbytis entellus*) and Monkey (*Rhesus macaque*) has increased in everywhere at this area and disturbing traditional subsistence agriculture and traditional cultivation so that local people are gradually avoiding this traditional pattern and shifting/involving in river-rafting activities. **N. Farooquee** stated that the traditional exchange of livestock and grains and maintenance of animal diversity by these villagers has also suffered drastically. But other hand, due to increasing of tourist in river rafting activities the opportunities of employment, infrastructure, economic transition and small enterprises will be increase at certain place which can improve the lifestyle, employment opportunities and economic status of local people.

Guideline/policies of Tourism and Forestry department regarding river rafting & camping

Department of forestry has designed the guideline/policies for River Rafting & Camping activities on the Ganga River and purely temporary for camp site from 15-Sep to 30-June every year. The camping prices are fixed by the forest department according to the activity areas. Forest department has fixed rate of camping sites according to areas is Rs 9/per sq. mtr up to 3,000 sq. mtr, Rs. 12/per sq. mtr varied from 3,000 to 7,000, while Rs 15/per sq. mtr above to 7,000 sq. mtr. (**Table- 8: Follow up guideline of Tourism and Forestry department for companies**).

Some major issues and their impact in river rafting as an ecotourism activity

S. N.	Issues	Impacts	Suggestion
1.	Cultural based Issues	Shifting traditional values to modern & cultivated way	Traditional culture pattern should be emphasize to introduce among tourists during activities
2.	Infrastructure	Create Ecological pressure and disturbance wild life	Introduce the concept of eco-friendly and eco-lodge for building and camps
3.	Traditional crop	Due to increasing of monkey and Langur in agriculture field	Camps owner and government should insure to local dishes in the menu of breakfast, lunch and dinner and purchase from local villages which can lead a major productivity of traditional crop and maintain demand & supply of the products.
4.	Area allocation for Camp activity	Registration for Camps & Rafts are increasing every year and it will lead to parochial animal habitat and daily activity on River Ganga	Camp should be in patches, so some space may be free for wild animal (Day & Night)
5.	Social Services	Seems lack of social contribution by the camp owner for the nearby villages	Several camp owner should ensures their contribution for social welfare and infrastructural development in their nearby villages
6.	Institutional Facilities	There is no proper training and capacity building programs provides by concern government department for local and staffs for safe rafting and better hospitality	Provide technical and non-technical training for the local villages, camp staff, raft guide and also awareness about the entire thing to tourists. Provide hospitality training and establishment an information flow. Participation & involvement of women should be includes in this sector.
7.	Natural Resources	Natural resources are utilizing overstep the mark by stakeholders and tourists during activities.	Development an eco-friendly strategy to consume. Natural resources and give a limited license for such activities as well as proper monitoring by government.
8.	Local Handloom/ Handicraft	Lack of awareness about such small scale business & no enterprises setup at certain area	Traditional Handloom & Handicraft as a small scale enterprise can be an option for improving socio-economic status of local people and can attract tourist.
9.	Live stock	Gradually decreasing at local level	Livestock products should be use in daily need of camp sites and owner should prefer local product to enhance their productivity and economy at local level.

Conclusion

As per the ground observation and analysis, river rafting and beach camping at Kaudiyala-Tapovan Ecotourism zone is growing rapidly and also arriving of tourists are increasing every year wherein about 20-30% foreigner tourists and 70-80% Indian tourists participates every season of river rafting and beach camping. Tourism department is directly responsible for operating and managing to all companies but their involvement is not seem properly because from Shivpuri to Kaudiyala there is only 02 public toilet on road head and there is no changing room, disposable dustbin, garbage pit available between Shivpuri to Kaudiyala road head. There is no control of Tourism Department for fix rate price of rafting and beach camping and also there is no check point between Kaudiyala-Tapovan during rafting and kayaking because some companies operate rafting illegal way.

Suggestion

River Rafting and beach camping should be operate by Tourism department and fully involve in all adventurous activities, tourist facilitation, garbage management and proper monitoring to each camp site and raft areas. Renewal processing for beach camp and rafting should be through single window. Generally three departments i.e. Forestry, Tourism, Revenue department are involve in operating and monitoring to rafting and camping site therefore every company owner has to face three stage for renewal licenses of rafting and camping. Government should organize a capacity building and awareness program among the local people about how they can reduce environmental impact along with increasing tourist on Ganga River and alongside areas.

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Table No-1 (Villages and their participation in Rafting)

S.N.	Name of Village	Household	Involvement in Rafting & Camping(family)		Local owner of camping & Rafting
			Directly	Indirectly	
1.	Kaudiyala	25	10	10	03-04 Family
2.	Singtali	55	20	05	05-08 Family
3.	Atali (Byasi)	60	20	25	05-07 Family
4.	Manjali	40	15	10	02-03 Family
5.	Shivpuri	58	25	20	10-15 Family
6.	Malakhunti	35	15	05	03-05 Family

Table No- 2 (Involvement of villagers)

Table No- 3 (Economic benefit through river rafting)

S.N.	Designation	Category	Salary (in %)			Remark
			05k-08k	08k-10k	10k-above	
1.	Raft Guide	Full salaried	20-25%	25-30%	50-55%	Minimum 5 years experiences Raft guide earn 10-15 thousand and above per month.
		Per Trip base	25-30%	35-40%	40-45%	Some companies hire raft guide for certain need and guide earn about 1000-1500 per trip of rafting.
2.	Camp Manager	Full Salaried	20-25%	20-25%	50-55%	Camp manager is a head of whole camp and they monitor all camp staff and facilitate to guests at camp site.
2.	Cook	Full Salaried	50-55%	30-35%	15-20%	Mostly cook is the head of kitchen and they also monitor to helper & serviceman. Some owners gives half salary during unseasonal.
3.	Helper	Full Salaried	75-80%	20-25%	-	Work of helper is to assist kitchen cook and clean utensils. Some owners gives half salary during unseasonal
4.	Serviceman	Full Salaried	60-65%	25-30%	10-15%	Serviceman provides all kind of hospitality/ services to all tourists.
5.	Potter	Full Salaried	75-80%	20-25%	-	Work of potter is to carry luggage of tourists from camp to road.
6.	Raft Guide Assistant	Temporary	80-85%	15-20%	-	Raft guide assistant help to raft guide during raft. They are unskilled that time.

Table- 4: Permit of License for Rafting and Camping

S.N.	Permit Issued Year	Number of Companies	No. of Rafts	No. of Camping + Rafts (Both)
1	1998	16	38	11
2	1999	17	40	12
3	2000	22	53	18
4	2001	24	62	16
5	2002	26	66	22
6	2003	29	74	22
7	2004	36	96	22
8	2005	42	126	24
9	2006	53	145	24
10	2007	74	162	20
11	2008	105	272	24
12	2009	102	257	24
13	2010	123	309	24
14	2011	134	326	24
15	2012	126	322	30
16	2013	102	324	34
17	2014 (Till 6 ^o oct 14)	50	175	24

Source: - Forestry Department, *Muni Ki Reti, Rishikesh*

Table- 5 statics data permit of License for Rafting and Camping

Table- 6: Follow up guideline of Tourism and Forestry department by companies

S.N.	Institutional Norms or / Instruction	Do	Don't	Remark
1.	Vegetarian food	✓	X	Non-vegetarian is strictly prohibited but some tourists bring packed non-vegetarian food from market and eat at beach camp.
2.	Alcoholic	X	✓	As above same
3.	Animal Hunting	X	✓	Strictly prohibited and no case seen by forestry and tourism department.
4.	Campfire/ Bonfire	✓	X	Only one bonfire allows by Forestry at each night for each company From 15 Feb-June not allow to bonfire at night to any company due to cause of spread fire.
5.	Dry Pit	✓	X	Most of the company's latrine is dry pit and they don't use of water, only uses to lime and sand. But some owner has permanent latrine and soak pit.
6.	Heavy sound	X	✓	Heavy sound are fully prohibited and as per observation and discussion with forest staff nobody use heavy sound at beach camp but they use only light sound like guitar, cell phone music etc.
7.	Light	X	✓	Any camp owner cannot use permanent or temporary electric light at camp site but they can use only hanging (Kerosine) light outside of the tent with dim light. Hanging light is not allowed Inside the tent.
8.	Fishing	X	✓	Strictly prohibited

Table- 7: Statistics of arrival of tourists before and after disaster:-

S.N.	Operating Year	Indian Tourists	Foreign Tourists
1.	2012-13	37,176	2,612
2.	2013-14	34,881	3,067
	Total	72,057	5,679

Source: - Department of Forestry, Uttarakhand